

O'ZBEKISTONDA TURAR JOY BINOLARINING ENERGIYA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDA XALQARO STANDARTLARDAN FOYDALANISH

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Annotatsiya. Hozirgi kunda yurtimizda binolarning energiya samaradorligini oshirish maqsadida keng ko'lamli ishlar jadal tarzda olib borilmoqda. Jumladan, mamlakatimizda yangi qurilayotgan va mavjud binolarni energiya samaradorligini oshirish yo'lida bir qancha ishlar amalga oshirilayapdi. Ushbu maqolamizda hozirgi kunda dolzarb muammolardan biri sanalayotgan energiya resurslarini tejashda binolarning energiya samaradorligini ahamiyati hamda energiya samaradorligini oshirish yo'llari to'g'risida ma'lumot keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar. Energiya samaradorlik, energiya, isitish, izolyatsiya, Energy Star
Abstract. Nowa days, large-scale works are being carried out intensively in order to increase the energy efficiency of buildings in our country. In particular, in our country, a number of works are being carried out to improve the energy efficiency of newly constructed and existing buildings. In this article, we present information about the importance of energy efficiency of buildings and ways to increase energy efficiency in saving energy resources, which is considered one of the current problems. given.

Key words. Energy efficiency, energy, heating, insulation, Energy Star

Абстрактный. В настоящее время в нашей стране интенсивно проводятся масштабные работы по повышению энергоэффективности зданий. В частности, в нашей стране проводится ряд работ по повышению энергоэффективности вновь строящихся и существующих зданий. В данной статье мы представляем информацию о значении энергоэффективности зданий и путях повышения энергоэффективности при экономии энергии. энергетических ресурсов, что считается одной из актуальных проблем.

Ключевые слова. Энергоэффективность, энергия, отопление, изоляция, Energy Star

KIRISH. Dunyo aholisini soni va ular daromadlarining oshishi, urbanizatsiya jarayonlarining tezlashishi va shu bilan birga iste'mol tuzilmasida tegishli o'zgarishlarni hisobga olganda holda, 2030 yilga kelib aynan binolar sohasidagi energiya resurslariga bo'lgan talab 2,5 marta oshishi mumkin. Bunday shart-sharoitlarda talab va energiya ta'minoti o'rtasidagi tafovut o'sishining oldini olish, uy-joy, tijorat va ma'muriy binolarning energiya bilan uzluksiz ta'minlanishi hamda insonlarning ijtimoiy huquqini ta'minlash uchun ushbu sohada energiya samaradorligini yaxshilashga doir chora-tadbirlar majmuini ishlab chiqish lozim.

Yurtimizda axoli sonini ortishi bilan binolarga bo'lgan ehtiyoj ham ortib bormoqda ayniqsa turar joy binolariga bo'lgan talab mutanosib ravishda ortib boradi. O'zbekistondagi jami energiya iste'molining deyarli yarmi binolar

hissasiga to'g'ri kelmoqda. Shu bilan birga, rivojlangan mamlakatlarga nisbatan O'zbekistonda binolarning energiya iste'moli 2-2,5 marta ko'proqdir. Energiya bo'yicha ortiqcha yo'qotishlari odatda quyidagilar bilan izohlanadi: binolarni qurish va qayta tiklash jarayonida energiya sig'imi yuqori bo'lgan eskirgan uskunalardan foydalanish tufayli; binolarni qurish jarayonida foydalaniladigan materiallarning issiqlik himoya xususiyatlari pastligi; isitish va havoni konditsiyalash tizimlari samaradorligining pastligi; muhandislik kommunikatsiyalarining eskirganligi hamda o'zining texnik ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha energiya samaradorligining zamonaviy talablarga javob bermaydigan oldin qurilgan binolar ulushining ko'pligi.

1-diagramma. O'zbekistonda binolarning energiya iste'moli rivojlangan mamlakatlarga nisbatan 2-2,5 marta ko'proqdir (yiliga KWh-soat/m²)

Buni so'rovnomalar natijalari tasdiqlamoqda hamda ushbu so'rovnomalar asosida turli xil binolar uchun "energiya samaradorligi sxemasi" ishlab chiqishga muvaffaq bo'lishdi.

Yakka tartibdagi uy-joylar

Uy-joylarning 90%i 20 yil avval qurilgan bo'lib, u paytda energiya resurslariga

bo'lgan narx nisbatan past bo'lganligi sababli binolarning energiya samaradorligiga unchalik ahamiyat qaratilmagan: plastik romlar, issiqlik izolyatsiya materiallari, germetizatsiyalash chora-tadbirlari va boshqalar deyarli ishlatilmagan. O'rganilgan uy-joy binolarining 66%ida yog'och romlar o'rnatilgan (ikki qavatli plastik romlarning o'rnatilishi issiqlik iste'molini 20%ga kamaytirish imkonini beradi). Uy tomlarining 91,7%ida issiqlik izolyatsiyasi mavjud emas. Binolarni germetizatsiyalash chora-tadbirlari faqatgina 60% uylarda amalga oshirilgan.

Turar-joylarning energiya samaradorligini oshirish, quyidagi chora-tadbirlarni o'z ichiga oladi: yangi quriladigan binolar uchun qurilish me'yorlari, passiv energiya va deyarli energiya talab etmaydigan binolarni qurish, mavjud binolarni energiya tejamkorlik nuqtai nazaridan qayta jihozlash, qurilish sertifikatlashtirishini ham joriy etish. Halqaro energetika agentligining yakuniy statistik ma'lumotlariga ko'ra unga a'zo 19 mamlakatda yuqoridagi energiya samaradorlik sohasidagi siyosat hal qiluvchi ro'l o'ynadi, unga ko'ra 1990 yildan beri ushbu ko'rsatkich 1,3 % ni tashkil etdi. Bugungi kunda turar-joy binolarining zamonaviy tendensiyasi bu "yashil binolar" qurishdan iborat. Ushbu tendensiya doirasida dunyoda yagona standartlar ishlab chiqilmagan bo'lib bunga sabab jahon tajribasida binoning ekologik darajasini aniqlash yondashuvi ishlab chiqilmagan. O'zigagina tegishli bo'lgan standartlar faqatgina Buyuk Britaniya, Fransiya, Germaniya, Italiya, Avstraliya, Yaponiya va Xitoydagina mavjud. AQSHda "yashil binolar"ning to'rtta standarti amal qiladi. Ba'zi bir shtatlarda Ekologik qurilish Kengashi tomonidan tasdiqlangan binolar egalariга subsidiyalar beriladi. Ko'pgina shtatlarda qurilish me'yorlari har yili yangilab boriladi, chunki 2030 yilga qadar har quriladigan yangi binolarning energiya sarfini ikki maratoba kamaytirishdan iborat. Bir qator shaharlar binoning energiya tejamkorlik darajasini aniqlashning ENERGY STAR dasturi doirasida tekshirishni qonunan belgilab qo'ydi, unga ko'ra 1 dan 100 gacha va undan ortiq hamda maydoni 1000 m² ortiq bo'lgan binolar uchun mos jadvallardan iborat.1

Taqqoslash uchun: energiya samaradorligi yuqori bo'lgan zamonaviy isitish qozonlarining foydali ish koeffitsienti 91-95%ni tashkil etadi. Isitish qozonlarining 80,8%ining foydalanish muddati 10 yildan ziyodni tashkil qiladi. Shu o'rinda ta'kidlash kerakki, isitish qozonlarining o'rtacha foydalanish muddati 10 yildan oshmasligi lozim. Foydalanilayotgan isitish qozonlarining 94% ida avtomatlashtirilgan boshqaruv tizimi mavjud emas. Uy xo'jaligida o'rnatilgan issiq suv ta'minoti qozonlarining 67,7%i ham foydalanish muddati 10 yildan ko'p bulgan qozonlardir.

Xulosa. Xulosa qilib quydagilarni aytishimiz mumkin. Energiya samaradorlik sohasida jahonda yetarlicha tajriba va sinovlar amalga oshirilib kelinmoqda , ularni bizning Mamlakatimiz iqlim sharoitiga moslab ko'rib chiqish talab etiladi. Yuqorida sanab o'tilgan chora-tadbirlarni amalga oshirishda Yurtimiz olimlarning ham taklif va yechimlari inobatga olish talab etiladi. Dunyodagi

mamlakatlar tajribasidan kelib chiqib ulardagi yutuq va kamchiliklarni o'rganib chiqish va ularni bizning iqlim sharoitimizga moslab o'zlashtirish kerak. Albatta yuqoridagi barcha fikrlarni inobatga olishda Qurilish me'yor qoidalari va me'yoriy normativ hujjatlar talablariga ham rioya qilish kerak.

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